

AESTHETICS AND CONTRADICTION IN PRODUCT SEMANTICS

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ABSTRACT

We examined the relationship between product aesthetics and contradictory semantics in the Typical–Novel dimension. We conducted two experiments where participants evaluated pictures of chairs using the bivariate method and the four-quadrant method for measuring semantic contradiction in products. Analysis of experiment results showed that semantic contradiction (or being both typical and unique) is positively correlated with aesthetic preferences, and that semantic vagueness (or being neither typical nor unique) is negatively correlated with aesthetic preferences. Both typicality and uniqueness have inverted-U relationships with aesthetic preferences. In addition, we found asymmetric influence by typicality and uniqueness of products. A chair that is perceived to be semantically vague tend to be typical, rather than unique, while a chair that is perceived to be semantically contradictory tend to be slightly more unique than typical. Finally, we propose that the four-quadrant method is a better way for measuring contradiction in product semantics than the bivariate method.

Keywords: Product Semantics, Product Aesthetics, Contradiction

INTRODUCTION

Product appearance plays an important role in communicating messages and eliciting emotional responses from consumers (Bloch, 1995 ; Crilly et al., 2004). To measure meanings conveyed by products, semantic differential scales with bipolar adjectives are often used (Osgood, 1957). When a scale with bipolar adjectives (A–B) is used to measure product semantics, there is an implicit assumption that the meaning conveyed by a particular product lies somewhere in-between: more A (and less B), or less

A (and more B); but not both A and B. However, it is not difficult to find products that convey contradictory meanings. For example (Figure 1), the Louis Ghost Chair designed by Philippe Starck for Kartell is traditional in shape, but novel in the use of material; and the Block Lamp by Harri Koskinen conveys both warmness and coldness.

<i>Traditional or Modern?</i>	<i>Warm or Cool?</i>
<i>Louis Ghost Chair by Philippe Starck for Kartell</i>	<i>Block Lamp by Harri Koskinen</i>

Figure 1.

Early studies from Berlyne (1971) proposed that the relationship between arousals and hedonic value exhibits an inverted-U function, called the Wundt curve. He hypothesized that moderate level of arousal by stimuli that are midway between familiar-novel and simple-complex achieves the highest hedonic value. More recently, Hekkert (2006) elaborated about design aesthetics and concluded that the principles of pleasure in design include “unity in variety” and “most advanced, yet acceptable”. From these theoretical works and design examples from the industry, we can see that embedding contradiction might be an effective way to elicit pleasurable responses by introducing novelty into familiar product forms.

Contradiction can be defined as “a logical incompatibility between two or more propositions” (Contradiction, n.d.). Thereafter, we refer to the cases where an adjective and its antonym apply simultaneously as a “semantic contradiction”. For

our study on product semantics, we define semantic contradiction operationally as the situation where a participant perceives the products to simultaneously convey antonymous meanings.

MEASURING SEMANTIC CONTRADICTION IN PRODUCTS

Two approaches have been developed in the psychology literature for investigating attitudinal ambivalence (Jonas et al., 2000). The first approach, measurement of experienced ambivalence (also called “direct measurement”) hypothesizes that participants can detect and evaluate the “degree of objective ambivalence”. Several questions are usually used to inquire whether the participant has feeling of ambivalence. The value of ambivalence is obtained by averaging all the answers of participants on all questions. Typical questions might be:

- I have contradictory feelings towards X:
Strongly agree Strongly disagree
- My evaluation towards X is...:
Very confused -3-2-1 0 +1+2+3 Not confused at all

The second approach, formula-based measurement of ambivalence (also called “indirect measurement”) does not require the participant to detect ambivalent feelings. Instead, two independent questions are used to obtain evaluation of positive and negative feelings. An index of ambivalence is then calculated from the two values. Although many formulas have been developed for calculating the ambivalent index (Priester & Petty, 1996), the most widely used formula for attitudinal ambivalence research is $((P+N)/2) - |P-N|$ (Thompson et al., 1995), where P and N represent the level of positive feelings and that of negative feelings, respectively. Typical questions might be:

- My thought of X is:
Not positive at all Very positive;
Not negative at all Very negative.

Referring to these two types of approaches to the measurement of ambivalence, we developed two methods for measuring semantic contradiction in products. The four-quadrant method, as illustrated in Figure 2, attempts to measure perceived semantic contradiction directly, by asking participants to classify a stimulus into one of the four quadrants.

For example, contradiction in the bipolar adjectives “typical - unique” is measured by using the following four quadrants, where the first, second, third and fourth quadrants correspond to +T+U: both typical and unique, U: unique (but not typical), -T-U: neither typical nor unique, and T: typical (but not unique), respectively. This method seeks to differentiate between semantic contradiction (+T+U, where both adjectives are applicable) and semantic vagueness (-T-U, where neither are applicable) (Hung & Chen, 2009). In this study, the degrees of typicality, uniqueness, and semantic contradiction, and semantic vagueness for a particular stimulus are estimated by using the percentages of participants who classify the stimulus in quadrants T, U, +T+U, and -T-U. We will use the notions T%, U%, +T+U%, and -T-U% to denote the corresponding percentages.

Figure 2. Four-quadrant method

The bivariate method, which is adapted from the formula-based measurement of ambivalence, measure perceived semantic contradiction indirectly, by asking participants to rate a stimulus on typicality and uniqueness separately (in this study, by using nine-point scales). Then, the ambivalence index for a particular stimulus is calculated from ratings of typicality (t) and uniqueness (u), by using the formula $((t+u)/2) - |t-u|$.

- not at all typical very typical
- not at all unique very unique

Figure 3. Bivariate method

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

STIMULI

We choose “chair” as the product category for this research, because it is one of the most

representative products in design history with a very wide range of designs. We first collected 523 photos of chairs, from the book *1000 Chairs* (Fiell & Fiell, 1997), from websites of furniture companies, and by using search engines. Two experienced designers (with more than 5 years of experience) examined the chairs and eliminated those similar in shape to reduce the total number to 213. We then asked 5 senior students with design background to independently sort the chairs into groups according to similarities in shape. We then analyzed the sorting results by using the hierarchical clustering function in SPSS. Finally, we arrived at 88 representative chairs, of which 41 are from the book *1000 Chairs* (produced between 1900 and 1997) and 47 from the internet (produced during the last two decades).

PARTICIPANTS

The participants consisted of undergraduate and graduate students at Mingchi University of Technology in Taiwan. Two experiments were performed, each with 60 paid participants, who were 18 to 24 years old, and came from industrial design, engineering, and management departments. In order to prevent memory effects, each participant only participated in one experiment.

EXPERIMENT METHOD

We conducted two experiments to measure semantic contradictions by using images of the 88 representative chairs. In the first experiment, we applied the bivariate method for evaluating typicality and uniqueness independently with nine-point scales, as illustrated in Figure 3. Additionally, we also included a nine-point scale for measuring aesthetic preference (ugly-beautiful) (Hekkert et al., 2003).

After browsing all 88 chair images, a participant was asked to divide the chairs into three groups representing low, medium and high levels with respect to the scale. The participant was then asked to further divide each group into three subgroups, to arrive at a total number of 9 groups corresponding to the 9-point scale. The number of chairs was allowed to be uneven or void in each group. At the end, the participant was asked to review the grouping again, and to make adjustments where necessary. The participant performed the grouping tasks at his/her

own pace, and in general completed the grouping tasks in about an hour.

In the second experiment, we applied the four-quadrant method (Figure 2) to measure semantic contradictions, again by using images of the 88 representative chairs. The researcher first explained the four categories (typical, unique, both typical and unique, and neither typical nor unique). Again, after browsing all 88 chair images, the participant was asked to categorize the pictures into one of the four quadrants, without any detailed classification on the magnitude of feeling. The number of chairs was allowed to be uneven or void in each quadrant. Before confirming the categorization, the participant was allowed to adjust chairs among the four quadrants. Finally, researchers would inquire participants regarding pictures within the “both typical and unique” and “neither typical nor unique” quadrants to clarify reasons for the classification:

- Why do you feel that this chair is both typical and unique at the same time?
- What are the reasons for its typicality and uniqueness?
- Why do you feel that this chair is neither typical nor unique?

RESULTS

AESTHETIC PREFERENCE AND PERCEPTIONS OF SEMANTIC CONTRADICTION AND VAGUENESS

Analysis of the data from the two experiments revealed positive linear correlations (Spearman's rank correlation) between semantic contradiction and aesthetic preference. For Experiment 1 (Figure 4a), ambivalence indices calculated from bivariate typicality and uniqueness values exhibit medium level of positive linear correlation with aesthetic preference ($r=0.486$, $p=0.000^{**}$). Similarly, for Experiment 2 (Figure 4b), the percentage of participants that perceived semantic contradiction (+T+U) exhibits medium level of positive linear correlation with aesthetic preference ($r=0.516$, $p=0.000^{**}$). On the other hand, the percentage of participants that perceived semantic vagueness (-T-U) exhibits medium level of negative linear correlation with aesthetic preference (Figure 4c, $r=-0.465$, $p=0.000^{**}$). These results show that semantic contradiction and vagueness are both factors

influencing aesthetic preference. In general, when participants are able to perceive contradiction in product semantics, higher levels of perceived semantic contradiction correspond to higher aesthetic preference; whereas when participants are not able to make sense of the intended product semantics, higher levels of perceived semantic vagueness correspond to lower levels of aesthetic preference.

AESTHETIC PREFERENCE AND PERCEPTION OF TYPICALITY AND UNIQUENESS

We did not find significant linear correlation between aesthetic preference and either typicality or uniqueness. For Experiment 1 (the bivariate method), there is no significant correlation between aesthetic preference and typicality rating ($r=0.089$, $p=0.407$), nor between aesthetic preference and uniqueness rating ($r=0.078$, $p=0.469$), as shown in Figures 5a and 5b. For Experiment 2 (the four quadrant method), there is no significant correlation between aesthetic preference and the percentage of participants that perceived the stimulus to be typical ($r=0.012$, $p=0.909$), nor between aesthetic preference and the percentage of participants that perceived the stimulus to be unique ($r=0.116$, $p=0.283$), as shown in Figures 5c and 5d. After conducting further analysis by using the quadratic curve model in SPSS, we found that, for the bivariate method, the relationship between aesthetic preference and typicality resembles an inverted-U function (Figure 5a, $F=11.4$, $p=0.000^{**}$), and so does the relationship between aesthetic preference and uniqueness (Figure 5b, $F=10.3$, $p=0.000^{**}$). For the four-quadrant method, we found similar but weaker relationships (Figure 5c, $F=2.30$, $p=0.106$; Figure 5d, $F=6.02$, $p=0.004^{**}$). These findings are in line with the previous study tested by bipolar semantic differential method (Hung & Chen, 2009): Chairs with medium level of typicality/uniqueness correspond to higher scores of aesthetic preference; whereas highly typical or unique chairs near the two extremes correspond to lower scores in aesthetic preference.

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN BIVARIATE VARIABLES AND FOUR QUADRANT PERCENTAGES

Figure 6 shows the correlations between the bivariate variables t and u , the four quadrant percentages $-T-U\%$, $T\%$, $+T+U\%$, and $U\%$. As expected, typicality rating t shows positive linear correlations with $T\%$ (Figure 6c) and negative linear correlation with $U\%$ (Figure 6g); uniqueness rating u shows negative linear correlations with $T\%$ (Figure 6d) and positive linear correlation with $U\%$ (Figure 6h). What is more surprising is that semantic vagueness ($-T-U\%$) is positive linearly correlated with typicality rating t (Figure 6a) and negative linearly correlated with uniqueness rating u (Figure 6b). This means that semantic vagueness more likely occurs when a product is perceived to be traditional, than when it is perceived to be unique. Even more interesting is that semantic contradiction ($+T+U\%$) shows inverse U relationships with bivariate typicality t and uniqueness u , respectively (Figures 6e and 6f). In particular, semantic contradiction, which is positively correlated to aesthetic preference (Figure 4b), is best achieved by combining a median level of typicality (Figure 6e) and a slightly higher level of uniqueness (Figure 6f).

Results shown in Figure 6 seem to indicate asymmetric influences of perceived typicality and uniqueness levels. That is, although semantic vagueness ($-T-U$) implies a lack of both typicality and uniqueness, the experiments showed that a chair that is perceived to be semantically vague tend to be typical, rather than unique. In addition, semantic contradiction ($+T+U$) tend to be slightly more unique than typical. One possible explanation to this apparent unequal influence between uniqueness and typicality might be the concept of “markedness” in Linguistics research. Fraenkel & Schul’s research (2008) suggested that for any pair of antonymous adjectives, one is usually “remarkable” and the other is “unremarkable”. Remarkable words are usually complex, difficult, abnormal, and exhibit multidimensional correlation with a cluster of correlating properties (Haspelmath, 2006). Unremarkable words are usually typical, normal, positive, common, more neutral and not unique compared to remarkable words (Battistella 1996). In this research, the concept of uniqueness might be more “remarkable” than the concept of typicality.

Figure 4. Correlation of aesthetic preference with ambivalence index, semantic contradiction (+T+U %) and vagueness (-T-U %).

Figure 5. Correlation of aesthetic preference with typicality and uniqueness (where linear models are shown as solid lines, and quadratic curve models as dashed lines).

Figure 6. Correlations between Bivariate Variables t and u, and Four Quadrant Percentages -T-U%, T%, +T+U%, and U%.

	1a	1b	1c	1d		
Exp. 1	aesthetic preference	3.62	3.87	aesthetic preference	4.72	3.17
	typicality rating	7.65	7.22	typicality rating	2.12	2.83
	uniqueness rating	1.18	1.73	uniqueness rating	8.65	8.20
	ambivalence index	-2.05	-1.01	ambivalence index	-1.15	0.15
Exp. 2	U %	6.7	11.7	U %	76.7	68.3
	+T+U %	1.7	0	+T+U %	6.7	11.7
	T%	68.3	65.0	T%	11.7	11.7
	-T-U%	23.3	23.3	-T-U%	5.0	8.3

Table 1. Chairs with the highest percentage of typicality (T%) and uniqueness (U%).

	2a	2b	2c	2d	
Exp. 1	aesthetic preference	5.85	5.22	4.55	6.12
	typicality rating	4.62	5.58	4.25	6.37
	uniqueness rating	6.00	4.82	5.35	4.55
	ambivalence index	3.93	4.43	3.70	3.64
Exp. 2	U %	25.0	18.3	20.0	13.3
	+T+U %	48.3	48.3	46.7	40.0
	T%	15.0	25.0	18.3	30.0
	-T-U%	11.7	8.30	15.0	16.7

Table 2. Chairs with the highest percentage of contradictory semantics (+T+U%).

	3a	3b	3c	
Exp. 1	aesthetic preference	4.48	2.83	3.70
	typicality rating	6.15	5.60	5.92
	uniqueness rating	3.43	3.93	3.37
	ambivalence index	2.08	3.10	2.09
Exp. 2	U %	8.3	16.7	13.3
	+T+U %	13.3	21.7	13.3
	T%	26.7	15.0	28.3
	-T-U%	51.7	46.7	45.0

Table 3. Chairs with the highest percentage of insensitive (-T-U%).

Furthermore, we observed that the bivariate method does not clearly distinguish chairs that are perceived by most participants to be both typical and unique (+T+U%) and those perceived by most participants to be neither (-T-U%) when using the four-quadrant method. As shown in Figure 7, the uniqueness and typicality ratings for all chairs from the bivariate method exhibit an almost perfect negative correlation ($r = -0.94$, $p = 0.000^{**}$). When the chairs are labeled according to the results from the four-quadrant method—as "●", "x", "△", and "○" for those classified by the highest percentages of participants to be +T+U, -T-U, U, and T, respectively—we found that, although the points labeled "△" and "○" roughly lie within the second (U) and the fourth (T) quadrants as expected, the points labeled "●" and "x" do not separately lie within the first (+T+U) and the third (-T-U) quadrants, but mingle together near the origin. Therefore, we conjecture that the four-quadrant method might be better than the bivariate method for distinguishing contradiction and vagueness in product semantics.

Figure 7. Correlations between bivariate variables t and u , where the points are labeled according to results from the four-quadrant methods—chairs that were classified by the highest percentages of participants to be +T+U, -T-U, U, and T are labeled as "●", "x", "△", and "○", respectively.

CHARACTERISTICS OF CHAIRS IN EACH OF THE FOUR QUADRANTS

We now look closer at the chairs that are classified into the four quadrants in Experiment 2. Chairs

which were classified by the highest percentages of participants to be either typical or unique in four-quadrant method are shown in Table 1. The most typical chairs usually have four legs, a flat seat, and a vertical and flat back with no arms (1a, 1b). On the other hand, the most unique chairs usually lack clear features and structure of a typical chair. For example, the chair labeled 1c has a balloon in the place of its seat and legs. The chair labeled 1d appears to have grass exaggeratedly planted over the seat and back.

Chairs that were classified by the highest percentages of participants to be both typical and unique are shown in Table 2. During interviews conducted after the experiment, most participants could differentiate the characteristics of these chairs and explain the reasons for their decisions. The chair labeled 2a was perceived to be both typical and unique, because its upper half shapes like a typical wooden chair, and yet its lower half consists of rotating layers forming a spiral shape. Similarly, for the chair labeled 2c, the top half looks like a Windsor style chair, but the legs are replaced by modern-looking black boards, conveying a feeling of uniqueness and contrast. Furthermore, a leg of the chair labeled 2b chair is replaced by a walking stick to provide support while a user is standing up; while the chair labeled 2d makes double use of one of the legs as an umbrella stand and a flower pot, allowing water to drip from the umbrella into the pot. From interviews of participants and observations on characteristics of chairs, we observe two types of contradictory design:

1. A chair with physical parts that convey contradictory meanings (such as Table 2a and 2c).
2. A chair mainly in the form of a typical chair, but combined with small variations that embed abstract concepts or stories (such Table 2b and 2d).

In both experiments, we found that the first type of chairs have uniqueness scores higher than typicality scores, while the second type of chairs have typicality scores higher than uniqueness scores. Table 3 contains chairs that were classified by the highest percentages of participants to be neither typical nor unique in the four-quadrant method. We observed that participants had difficulty explaining

the intended messages conveyed by these chairs. Therefore, many participants' descriptions include not knowing, not understanding, not caring, or genuinely not having any feeling. The perceived semantic vagueness in these chairs makes them liable to lower aesthetic preference than chairs with contradictory semantics. For example, the chair labeled 3a, which is covered with a soft cloth, was not seen as typical or special in its design concept. A majority (51.7%) of the participants thought that it was "neither typical nor unique". For the chairs labeled 3b and 3c, almost half (45%) of participants did not know or could not understand why such appearances were designed, and could not relate to these design operations.

CONCLUSION

Analysis of experimental data showed that both semantic contradiction and semantic vagueness correlate with product aesthetics. Higher ambivalent indices correspond to higher levels of product aesthetics, so do higher percentages of being "both typical and unique." On the other hand, higher percentages of being "neither typical nor unique" correspond to lower levels of product aesthetics. No significant linear correlations are observed between product aesthetics and typicality scores or product aesthetics and uniqueness scores; instead, both resemble inverted-U relationships. Furthermore, we found asymmetric influences by typicality and uniqueness of products. For the chairs that are considered to be "both typical and unique" in the four-quadrant method, most are rated higher in uniqueness than in typicality in the bivariate method, while few are the other way around. For those contradictory designs with higher typicality scores and lower uniqueness scores, they usually have the physical form of a typical chair while embedding abstract concepts or stories to simultaneously exhibit the feeling of "both typical and unique". We propose that the four-quadrant method is a better way for measuring contradiction in product semantics than the bivariate method. By using the four quadrant method, participants can separate chairs that are "both typical and unique" and those

that are "neither typical nor unique." This was not possible when using the bivariate method. As we have shown in this study, semantic contradiction and semantic vagueness lead to opposite aesthetic responses from participants. Thus, it is important to separate these two cases so that the best ways to mix typicality and uniqueness can be further investigated.

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